

A rapid and validated RP-HPLC method for estimation of glimepiride in solid dosage form

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Abstract : A simple, accurate, rapid, precise and economic reverse phase high performance liquid chromatographic method was developed for estimation of glimepiride in tablet dosage form using C18 (5 μ m, 250 mm \times 4.6 mm) column. The mobile phase was a mixture of phosphate buffer (pH = 7.0 \pm 0.1) and acetonitrile in the ratio 40 : 60 v/v. The detection wavelength was 228 nm. The retention time was 1.9 min at a flow rate of 1 ml/min. The validation of the proposed method was carried out according to USP and ICH guidelines. The method was found to be linear ($r^2 = 0.9999$), precise (%RSD \leq 2), accurate (mean percentage recovery yields = 99.31) and selective. Due to its simplicity, accuracy and economic value, the proposed method can be used for routine quality control analysis of solid dosage forms of glimepiride.

Keywords : RP-HPLC, glimepiride, validation, RSD.

Introduction

Glimepiride is chemically 1-[4-[2-(3-ethyl-4-methyl-2-oxo-3-pyrroline-1-carboxamide)ethyl]phenyl sulphonyl]-3-(4-methylcyclohexyl) urea¹ and is an anti-diabetic agent which lowers the blood glucose level in type-II i.e. non-insulin dependant diabetes mellitus patients principally by stimulating the beta cells of pancreas. In prolonged use it provides overall glycemc control without appreciable increase in fasting insulin secretion. The drug is found to be ineffective in case of non-functioning beta cells of pancreas. It also offers advantages to diabetic patients with ischemic heart disease². A spectrophotometric method³ for estimation of glimepiride in tablet dosage form had been reported. HPLC method for estimation of glimepiride in pharmaceutical dosage form⁴ and in human plasma⁵ had also been reported. However, our method is precise, more rapid and economic in routine analysis of glimepiride formulations in pharmaceutical industry.

Results and discussion

The developed HPLC method provides a convenient and efficient method for the estimation of glimepiride in dosage form. The mobile phase gave a well resolved,

sharp peak for glimepiride with retention time of 1.9 min (Fig. 1). The system suitability was evaluated by making six replicate injections of the standard preparation and the peak response was recorded at optimized chromatographic conditions. The results were tabulated in Table 1. Accuracy of the method was calculated by percent mean recovery studies ($n = 3$). The calculation of the standard spike to the sample was 1.7 to 4.9 μ g/ml of glimepiride. The mean recovery observed was 99.31%. The percent RSD with respect to accuracy of recovery test was 0.45 (Table 2) which showed that the method was free from interference of the excipients used in the formulation. There was good repeatability of proposed method as the precession (%RSD) of the method was less than 2% for the drug. The percent RSD with respect to peak area, peak retention time and amount for standard solutions were 0.2, 0.1 and 0.2 respectively (Table 1). A linear relationship was obtained in the concentration range of 80 to 120% of assay concentration of drug and the regression factor (R^2) was found to be 0.9999 (Fig. 2). The method was satisfactory with respect to ruggedness and robustness. The limit of detection (LOD) and the limit of quantitation (LOQ) were found to be 0.0618 and 0.1874 μ g/ml respectively.

Fig. 1. Typical chromatogram of standard glimepiride.

Table 1. Results of method validation

Sl. no.	Subject	Component	Result	Limit
1.	Plate count by 5 σ method	Glimepiride	4039	>2000
2.	Symmetry factor	Glimepiride	1.09	0.8–1.5
3.	Precession %RSD for 6 replicate injections	Peak area	0.2	<2%
		Peak RT (Standard)	0.1	
		Amount	0.2	
4.	Regression factor from linearity curve	Glimepiride	0.9999	≤ 1
5.	Accuracy %RSD for three different concentration solutions	Glimepiride	0.45%	<2%

Table 2. Table for recovery studies^a (accuracy)

Average actual concn. of 100% sample solution	Solution	Concn. from spike solution ($\mu\text{g/ml}$)	Excess amount (%)	Average actual assay of 100% sample solution (mg/tablet)	Assay from spike solution (mg)	Excess amount (%)	Recovery difference (%)	Accuracy (%)	%RSD
15.40	A	17.10	11.04	2.03	2.25	10.84	0.20	99.80	0.45
	B	18.60	20.77		2.43	19.70	1.07	98.93	
	C	20.30	31.82		2.66	31.03	0.79	99.21	

^aResults are calculated from average of six replicate injections of each of the three spike solutions.

Note

Fig. 2. Linearity and range graph of glimepiride.

Experimental

Chemicals :

Standard glimepiride was obtained from Alcon Biosciences Pvt. Ltd., Gujarat. Potassium di-hydrogen phosphate and di-potassium hydrogen phosphate of AR grade and acetonitrile of HPLC grade were purchased from Merck Ltd., Mumbai. HPLC grade water was obtained from Arium 611UV water purification system of Sartorius, Germany.

Chromatographic conditions :

An Waters HPLC (515 pump; 2487 dual λ absorbance detector) system was used for analysis. The method was carried out on a C18 (5 μ m, 250 \times 4.6 mm) column. The mobile phase used was a mixture of 40 volumes of a phosphate buffer solution (adjusted pH 7 \pm 0.1) with orthophosphoric acid and 70 volumes of acetonitriles. The mobile phase was filtered through a 0.45 μ m membrane filter (Millipore) and degassed. A rheodyne injector with a 20 μ l loop was used for the injection of standard and sample solution. Detection was done at 228 nm. The analysis was carried out at room temperature (about 25 $^{\circ}$ C) and all data were acquired and processed using Empower 2 software.

Procedure :

Standard stock solution was prepared containing 0.4 mg/ml of glimepiride in mobile phase. Final working stan-

dard solution was made by diluting stock solution to 16 μ g/ml of glimepiride in mobile phase. 20 tablets each containing 2.0 mg (label claim) of glimepiride were weighed and finally powdered. A quantity of powder equivalent to 10 mg of glimepiride was weighed accurately and transferred to a 25 ml volumetric flask. About 15 ml of mobile phase was taken and sonicated for 20 min and volume was made up to the mark by mobile phase. This solution was filtered (Whatman No. 1) and further diluted to 16 μ g/ml of glimepiride (theoretical value). The content of standard and sample solution was then filtered through 0.45 μ m syringe filter. Chromatograms of standard solution (six replicates) and sample solution (two replicates) were recorded. A typical chromatogram of glimepiride is presented in Fig. 1. The retention time of glimepiride was 1.9 min. The concentration of glimepiride in sample was obtained by comparing with the standard solution.

Method validation :

The analytical method was validated as per USP⁶ and ICH⁷ guidelines for parameter like accuracy, precision, ruggedness, robustness, linearity and range. To ensure reliability and accuracy of the proposed method, recovery studies were carried out by mixing a known quantity of standard drug at three different levels (110, 120 and 130% of assay value labeled as A, B, C respectively) with pre-analyzed samples and contents were re-analyzed

by the proposed method. Results are tabulated in Table 2. Precision of the method was studied by making six injections of standard solutions and their percent relative standard deviation (%RSD) was calculated (Table 1). Linearity and range of the method was determined by analyzing standard solutions containing 12.846–19.269 µg/ml of glimepiride. The limit of detection (LOD) and limit of quantitation (LOQ) of the method was determined by injecting progressively low concentration of the standard solution with optimized chromatographic conditions. Ruggedness of the method was determined by carrying out the experiments by different instruments like Waters HPLC 600 pumps, Merck Hitachi HPLC LaChrome pumps L-7100 with Merck Hitachi UV LaChrome detector L-7400 etc. by different operators, using similar type columns of different make. The robustness of the method was also determined by making slight changes in chromatographic conditions like composition ($\pm 5\%$) and pH ($\pm 0.1\%$) of mobile phase.

Conclusion :

The proposed HPLC method was found to be simple, accurate, precise, reproducible, rugged, robust, linear, rapid and economical and can be used in quantitative analysis of the drug in tablet dosage form.

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